

A STUDY ON THE DETERMINATION OF STOCHASTIC REINFORCEMENT PERMEABILITY IN CONSTANT INJECTION PRESSURE CONDITIONS

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SUMMARY

We report two effects in permeability measurement: the error introduced by assuming constant injection pressure and the evolution of permeability dispersion with volume fraction. For the first, we proposed a simple modelling approach. For the second, our results showed a reduction in the dispersion with higher fibre volume fractions, which we believe is due to the reduction of the variability of the size of the pores of the reinforcement.

Keywords: Stochastic modelling, permeability, constant pressure, RTM, radial flow.

INTRODUCTION

In all liquid moulding processes we need to know permeability in order to model the flow behaviour of the resin as it impregnates the preform in resin transfer moulding or similar processes. Hence, permeability measurements are critical for accurate flow modelling [1]. Although permeability has been studied for a long time, there is still no agreement regarding the best experimental methods and procedures to measure it.

Permeability can be measured in constant injection pressure (CIP) or constant flow rate (CFR) experiments. Both have disadvantages: CFR generates ever increasing pressures that may lead to cavity thickness variations and requires complex equipment to be put together; CIP experiments are easier to set-up but they might induce measurement and calculation errors.

The purpose of our work is to determine the unsaturated permeability of a carbon fibre woven fabric using an experimental CIP method and radial flow. However, pressure is not constant because we use a set of values obtained over time instead of a specific value for the injection pressure. Thus, to determine the permeability we use the whole real information about the injection pressure, therefore introducing less error in the calculations.

The dispersion of our results decreases with the increase of the fibre volume fraction. Hoes *et al.* [2] have shown that nesting of layers has a strong influence on the scatter in permeability values. We believe that the reduction of the size of the empty spaces also plays an important role: as the fibre volume increases the size of each empty space becomes smaller and also less variable, and so do the permeability values.

METHODS

The set-up used in this work was the aluminium permeability rig that can be seen in Figure 1, based on the work by Hoes *et al.* [3]. Reinforcement is placed in the circular cavity, whose height is controlled by eight spacer discs. Four pressure transducers *Keller PR-21S* are placed on the back of the bottom plate: one in the middle and the other three 95mm from the centre, at 90°, 45° and 0°, identified as sensors 1, 2, 3 and 4, respectively.

Figure 1: On the left, the rig assembled in the pressing machine. On the right, top view of the bottom plate with each of the pressure sensors identified.

The spacer discs are inserted in the surface that surrounds the cavity in the bottom plate of the aluminium rig. The thickness of each disc determines the height of the cavity where the fabric layers are placed. We used discs with thicknesses of 2.01mm, 1.71mm and 1.45mm.

The fabric we used is a carbon fibre weave with a 2×2 braid pattern, Figure 2.

Figure 2: Carbon fibre fabric: schema to the left and real image to the right.

Firstly we cut the fabric in squares larger than the 320mm in diameter of the mould cavity. The fabric coil was hung with its axis laid horizontally. Defining this axis as the xx axis (referred to in this work as angle 0° of the fibres) and its perpendicular as the yy axis (referred to in this work as angle 90° of the fibres), all the cut squares were handled always keeping this orientation.

Before being cut into circles or placed in the cavity of the mould, the fabric layers need to be aligned to keep the 0° of the mesh parallel to the xx axis and the 90° lined up with the yy axis. For that, we used a wooden platform with two mutually perpendicular axes drawn that allowed lining up each one of the fabric layers. Placing each layer on the plate, we lined up the fibres with the axes with the aid of a ruler.

So that the fabric layers had the size and shape of the base of the mould cavity, they were cut using a circular blade pressed against the fabric inside the pressing machine. We cut a

hole of 8mm in diameter in the centre of each layer to allow the resin to fall directly into the central pressure sensor during the permeability experiments, thus measuring the injection pressure.

The reinforcement used in each experiment was made of seven aligned circular fabric layers. Together, the seven layers had a thickness of 2.4mm. Hence, even with the 2.01mm spacer discs we could prevent the draining of the flow between the surface of the upper layer and the upper plate of the rig.

After placing the carbon reinforcement in the cavity and closing the pressing machine, an unsaturated polyester resin (*Norsodyne I 16333*) was injected in the porous medium through the inlet in the middle of the top plate of the rig, using a pressure pot. The pressure values detected by each sensor were acquired by means of a data acquisition system.

After every experiment, the press and the pressure pot tube were carefully cleaned with acetone so that the resin could flow in the same conditions every time.

We can calculate the permeability of the reinforcement with the following expression, derived from Darcy's law and the equation of the conservation of mass [4]:

$$K = \frac{r^2 \left(2 \ln \frac{r}{r_0} - 1 \right) + r_0^2}{4t\Delta P} \mu \phi. \quad (1)$$

This equation relates the permeability with the porosity of the reinforcement, ϕ , the viscosity of the fluid, μ , the injection pressure, ΔP , the radius of the inlet, r_0 , and the position of the flow front, r , at a given instant t .

Figure 3 shows the evolution of the injection pressure with time (see Appendix A): we cannot say that the injection pressure is constant. Hence, when using a fixed value for the injection pressure we are ignoring information since the injection pressure is a function of time. Therefore, error is introduced in the calculations.

Figure 3: Typical evolution of the injection pressure with time.

Thus, our intention was to calculate the permeability considering all the evolution of the injection pressure with time. For that, Equation (1) needed to be adapted (Equation (2); see derivation in Appendix B).

$$r = r_0 * \exp \left[\frac{1}{2} W \left(\frac{4tPK - \mu\phi r_0^2}{\mu\phi r_0^2 e} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \right] \quad (2)$$

If we use all the pressure values obtained for every instant t , Equation (2) defines the position of the flow front in time.

Thus, considering the pressures obtained from the reading of sensor 1, and defining an initial estimate for the permeability, K_i , we obtain an estimated plot of a flow front as well as instant t_i that corresponds to the position of sensors 2, 3 and 4, i.e. $r = 95\text{mm}$. Knowing the exact instants, t_s ($s=2, 3, 4$), when the resin reaches each one of those sensors, we can determine the permeabilities for each direction, K_s : because the position of the flow front is the same in both cases ($r = 95\text{mm}$), Equation (2) with t_i and K_i is equal to the same equation with t_s and K_s , implying that:

$$t_i K_i = t_s K_s. \quad (3)$$

Thus, we can calculate the permeability K_s that allows the graph of the flow front to pass on the point (t_s, r) .

RESULTS

As explained, after solving Equation (2) using the time evolving pressure obtained by sensor 1 for every instant t , the viscosity of the resin measured before the experiment and the porosity of the reinforcement, and choosing an initial estimate for K , we obtain the graph of a flow front, where we can determine the instant that corresponds to the position 95mm. With these data and Equation (3) we determine the permeabilities in each of the three directions we considered: 0° , 45° and 90° .

We considered that resin reached each when the pressure is equal or higher than 500Pa.

In Tables 1, 2 and 3 are the values obtained in each experiment for the viscosity (μ) and temperature of the resin, for the total mass of the seven layers of the carbon fabric, for the porosity (ϕ), and for the permeability (K), using the spacer discs of 2.01mm, 1.71mm and 1.45mm, respectively. In the last column of each table is the permeability obtained with Equation (1), using $r = 95\text{mm}$, $r_0 = 3.4\text{mm}$, $\Delta P = 4.2 \times 10^5 \text{Pa}$, the pressure in the pressure pot.

The fact that sometimes sensor 2 corresponds to the 0° of the mesh instead of the 90° (and sensor 4 to the 90° instead of the 0°) means that we turned the reinforcement 90° to test if the results were independent of the orientation of the fibres in relation to the mould.

Figures 4 to 6 represent the results obtained for the permeability (using our methodology) in relation to the fibre volume, for 0° , 45° and 90° of the mesh, respectively, as well as the models obtained by Brusckhe and Advani [5] and Kozeny and Carman [5]. Moreover, the modified model of Kozeny and Carman (K-C) considered by Pan *et al.* [6] is also represented: instead of using the powers of 3 and 2 for the porosity and the fibre volume, respectively, the powers are determined by the linear regression of the results.

Although the original Brusckhe and Advani model does not use empirical parameters, we were forced to use a proportional constant (determined by linear regression) in order to fit the model to our results. The constants of the other models have been equally determined by linear regression.

Table 1: Values obtained in the four experiments made with the 2.01mm spacer discs.

Exp.	μ (Pa·s)	Resin temp. (°C)	Mass of the reinf. (kg)	ϕ	Sensor	Angle (°)	t (s)	K ($10^{-12}m^2$)	K' ($10^{-12}m^2$)
1	0.523	15.8	0.15922	0.480	2	90	3531	2.88	2.16
					3	45	1721	5.90	4.44
					4	0	837	12.2	9.12
2	0.525	16.0	0.15783	0.485	2	0	541	18.6	14.3
					3	45	475	21.2	16.3
					4	90	474	21.2	16.3
3	0.501	16.5	0.15824	0.483	2	0	831	11.7	8.86
					3	45	829	11.7	8.88
					4	90	818	11.9	9.00
4	0.533	16.0	0.15759	0.485	2	90	3447	3.01	2.28
					3	45	2998	3.46	2.62
					4	0	1387	7.48	5.67

μ : viscosity; ϕ : porosity; K : permeability obtained with our methodology; K' : permeability obtained with Equation (1)

Table 2: Values obtained in the four experiments made with the 1.71mm spacer discs.

Exp.	μ (Pa·s)	Resin temp. (°C)	Mass of the reinf. (kg)	ϕ	Sensor	Angle (°)	t (s)	K ($10^{-12}m^2$)	K' ($10^{-12}m^2$)
5	0.531	15.6	0.15895	0.386	2	90	2791	2.96	2.23
					3	45	2455	3.37	2.54
					4	0	1366	6.06	4.56
6	0.511	16.3	0.15770	0.391	2	0	2394	3.38	2.54
					3	45	2835	2.85	2.14
					4	90	4085	1.97	1.49
7	0.540	16.2	0.15777	0.391	2	90	4721	1.81	1.36
					3	45	2699	3.16	2.38
					4	0	1579	5.41	4.07
8	0.510	16.9	0.15905	0.386	2	90	1311	6.01	4.57
					3	45	954	8.28	6.28
					4	0	891	8.86	6.72

μ : viscosity; ϕ : porosity; K : permeability obtained with our methodology; K' : permeability obtained with Equation (1)

Table 3: Values obtained in the four experiments made with the 1.45mm spacer discs.

Exp.	μ (Pa·s)	Resin temp. (°C)	Mass of the reinf. (kg)	ϕ	Sensor	Angle (°)	t (s)	K ($10^{-12}m^2$)	K' ($10^{-12}m^2$)
9	0.507	16.1	0.15945	0.279	2	90	4525	1.26	0.95
					3	45	4203	1.35	1.02
					4	0	1215	4.73	3.54
10	0.511	16.3	0.15968	0.278	2	0	1015	5.75	4.36
					3	45	2231	2.61	1.98
					4	90	3044	1.91	1.45
11	0.526	16.1	0.15848	0.283	2	90	2303	2.63	1.97
					3	45	1820	3.33	2.49
					4	0	1078	5.60	4.20
12	0.506	16.1	0.15820	0.285	2	0	1832	3.20	2.39
					3	45	4867	1.20	0.90
					4	90	4707	1.24	0.93

μ : viscosity; ϕ : porosity; K : permeability obtained with our methodology; K' : permeability obtained with Equation (1)

Figure 4: Graph of the permeabilities obtained for the 0° of the mesh, relative to the fibre volume.

Figure 5: Graph of the permeabilities obtained for the 45° of the mesh, relative to the fibre volume.

Figure 6: Graph of the permeabilities obtained for the 90° of the mesh, relative to the fibre volume.

Bruschke and Advani's model is:

$$K = c \frac{r_f^2 (1-L^2)^2}{3 L^3} \left(\frac{3L \operatorname{ArcTg} \left(\sqrt{\frac{1+L}{1-L}} \right)}{\sqrt{1-L^2}} + \frac{L^2}{2} + 1 \right)^{-1}, \quad L = \sqrt{\frac{4V_f}{\pi}}, \quad (4)$$

where constant c can take the values 24.2, 20.3 or 18.4 for the 0° , 45° and 90° of the mesh, respectively. V_f is the fibre volume fraction and r_f is the radius of a fibre. We used $r_f = 7\mu\text{m}$.

The Kozeny-Carman model is defined by:

$$K = c \frac{(1-V_f)^3}{V_f^2}, \quad (5)$$

where c is $3.92 \times 10^{-11} \text{m}^2$, $2.80 \times 10^{-11} \text{m}^2$ or $2.39 \times 10^{-11} \text{m}^2$, depending on the angle of the mesh (0° , 45° and 90° , respectively).

The modified Kozeny-Carman model is:

$$K = c \frac{(1-V_f)^a}{V_f^b}, \quad (6)$$

where a is -5.0, -0.28 or -3.2, b is equal to -11, -4.9 or -9.5, and c is $2.2 \times 10^{-16} \text{m}^2$, $2.8 \times 10^{-13} \text{m}^2$ or $1.3 \times 10^{-15} \text{m}^2$ for the 0° , 45° and 90° of the mesh, respectively.

DISCUSSION

We have observed (from Tables 1 to 3) that results are consistently higher in the 0° fabric orientation regardless of the mould direction used (i.e. rotating the fabric 90° in the mould produces a consistent measurement). Thus, we are confident that our permeability rig does not have a preferential flow orientation.

The values of the permeability presented very high relative standard-deviations (RSD) (Table 4) when compared to works like [3] and [6] where the RSD are less than 25%. This fact is probably due to the type of material and the relatively smaller number of experiments.

Table 4: Relative standard-deviation of the permeability for different angles of the mesh.

Spacer disc (mm)	RSD		
	0°	45°	90°
2.01	36.7%	74.7%	89.5%
1.71	38.2%	58.6%	61.2%
1.45	24.3%	48.2%	37.4%

Analyzing the RSD and Figure 7, we can see that the scatter of the results decreases with the increase of the fibre volume fraction (the decrease of the thickness of the spacer discs). This fact is probably due to the reduction of the size of the empty spaces: as the fibre volume increases and, consequently, the porosity decreases, the size of each empty space

becomes smaller and also less variable, which is expressed in a less scattered permeability. Due to the high dispersion of the permeability results, no conclusion could be drawn as to the material's anisotropy, and isotropy can be assumed.

Figure 7: Means and respective standard deviations of the permeabilities obtained for the different angles of the mesh, with the 2.01mm, 1.71mm and 1.45mm spacer discs.

Analysing Table 5 we can conclude that of the three models used, the modified Kozeny-Carman is the least valid and Brusckhe and Advani's is the one that comes closer to the results of this work, except for the case of the 0°, where the K-C model fits better. However, Brusckhe and Advani's model does not present good coefficients of determination – the large relative errors of the data do not allow the validation of any model.

Table 5: Coefficients of determination, R^2 , for each model and angle.

Model	R^2		
	0°	45°	90°
Brusckhe and Advani	0.705	0.601	0.545
Kozeny-Carman	0.711	0.524	0.420
Modified K-C	0.434	0.339	0.299

In the case of the 0°, the modified K-C model, besides being the one that presents the lowest coefficient of determination, is unacceptable to model the permeability in this range of fibre volume fraction, because permeability decreases with the increase of the fibre volume, which is not what happens with this model (Figure 4).

The relative errors of each linear regression increase (because R^2 decreases) with the angle of the mesh, which may be a result of the larger scatter of the permeability verified to happen with that same increase (Table 4).

Most importantly, we showed that using Equation (1) the permeability values are about 25% smaller than the ones obtained using our methodology. Also, they present higher RSD and lower coefficients of determination for the three models we used.

CONCLUSIONS

We determined the unsaturated permeability of a carbon fibre woven fabric using an experimental method of constant injection pressure and radial flow. However, instead of

using a fixed value for the injection pressure we used a set of values that define the injection pressure, introducing less error in the calculations.

Our results showed a high scatter, but we were able to detect a pattern: the dispersion of our results decreases with the increase of the fibre volume, which we believe is due to the reduction of the size of the empty spaces in the reinforcement as the fibre volume increases.

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Appendix A: Evolution of the injection pressure with time

Applying Poiseuille's law to the flow in the inlet tube [7]:

$$Q = -\frac{\pi R_t^4}{8\mu} \frac{P_{inj} - P_{pot}}{L_t}, \quad (7)$$

where R_t and L_t are the tube's inner radius and length, and P_{inj} is the injection pressure and P_{pot} is the pressure inside the pressure pot.

Inside the mould, flow rate is given by Darcy's law:

$$Q = -\frac{\pi R_i^2 K}{\mu} \frac{P_m - P_{inj}}{r}, \quad (8)$$

where R_i is the radius of the inlet, r is the position of the flow front, and P_m is the pressure in the mould. Because both flow rates are the same:

$$\frac{\pi R_t^4}{8\mu} \frac{P_{inj} - P_{pot}}{L_t} = \frac{\pi R_i^2 K}{\mu} \frac{P_m - P_{inj}}{r}, \quad (9)$$

the injection pressure is not constant, since it depends on the position of the flow front:

$$P_i = \frac{8L_t R_i^2 K P_m + r R_t P_{pot}}{8L_t R_i^2 K + r R_t}. \quad (10)$$

Fill time follows from Equation (10) and Darcy's law, considering $r = 0$ at $t = 0$:

$$t = \frac{\mu \phi}{K (P_{pot} - P_m)} \frac{r^2}{2} + \frac{8\mu \phi L_t R_i^2}{R_t^4 (P_{pot} - P_m)} r. \quad (11)$$

Thus, solving Equation (11) in relation to r and substituting in Equation (10) we have the expression that relates time with the injection pressure, and that explains Figure 3:

$$P_i = \frac{8\mu \phi L_t R_i^2 K (P_m - P_{pot})}{\sqrt{64\mu^2 \phi^2 L_t^2 R_i^2 K^2 + 2\mu \phi R_t^8 K t (P_{pot} - P_m)}} + P_{pot} \quad (12)$$

Appendix B: Derivation of Equation (2)

Isolating the elements with r in one member and dividing both members by $r_0^2 e$, where $e = \exp(1)$, Equation (1) becomes:

$$\frac{4tPK - \mu\phi r_0^2}{\mu\phi r_0^2 e} = \frac{r^2}{r_0^2 e} \left(2 \ln \frac{r}{r_0} - 1 \right). \quad (13)$$

If we apply the rule $A = e^{\ln A}$ to $\frac{r^2}{r_0^2 e}$, we have:

$$\frac{4tPK - \mu\phi r_0^2}{\mu\phi r_0^2 e} = \left(2 \ln \frac{r}{r_0} - 1 \right) \exp \left(2 \ln \frac{r}{r_0} - 1 \right). \quad (14)$$

If we call the left member of Equation (14) F , what we have is $F = f(r)e^{f(r)}$, where $f(r) = 2 \ln(r/r_0) - 1$. This equation is solved with Lambert's *omega* function: $F = f(r)e^{f(r)} \Rightarrow f(r) = W(F)$. Thus, Equation (14) becomes:

$$2 \ln \frac{r}{r_0} - 1 = W \left(\frac{4tPK - \mu\phi r_0^2}{\mu\phi r_0^2 e} \right), \quad (15)$$

which can be solved in relation to r , giving Equation (2):

$$r = r_0 * \exp \left[\frac{1}{2} W \left(\frac{4tPK - \mu\phi r_0^2}{\mu\phi r_0^2 e} \right) + \frac{1}{2} \right].$$

References

1. S. Scholz, J. W. Gillespie_Jr., D. Heider, Measurement of Transverse Permeability Using Gaseous and Liquid Flow, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 38, 2034-2040, 2007.
2. K. Hoes, D. Dinescu, H. Sol, R. S. Parnas, S. Lomov, Study of Nesting Induced Scatter of Permeability Values in Layered Reinforcement Fabrics, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 35, 1407-1418, 2004.
3. K. Hoes, D. Dinescu, H. Sol, M. Vanheule, R. S. Parnas, Y. Luo, I. Verpoest, New Set-Up for Measurement of Permeability Properties of Fibrous Reinforcements for RTM, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing* 33, 959-969, 2002.
4. C. D. Rudd, A. C. Long, K. N. Kendall, C. G. E. Mangin, Chapter 8: Process Modelling in *Liquid Moulding Technologies: Resin transfer moulding, structural reaction injection moulding and related processing techniques*, Woodhead Publishing Ltd., Abington, England, 1997.
5. S. G. Advani, E. M. Sozer, Chapter 4: Constitutive Laws and Their Characterization in *Process Modeling in Composites Manufacturing*, Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, USA, 2003.
6. R. Pan, Z. Liang, C. Zhang, B. Wang, Statistical Characterization of Fiber Permeability for Composite Manufacturing, *Polymer Composites* 21 (6), 996-1006, 2000.
7. N. C. Correia, *Analysis of the Vacuum Infusion Moulding Process*, PhD Thesis, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, England, 2004.